

Cluster-Wise Hyperparameter Optimization Enhances Regional Rainfall–Runoff Modeling with Deep Learning: A Robust CAMELS-US Benchmark: Supplementary Materials

Farzad Hosseini ^{a,*}, Cristina Prieto^a, Cesar Alvarez^a

^a*Instituto de Hidráulica Ambiental de la Universidad de Cantabria (IHCantabria), 39011 Santander, Cantabria, Spain*

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Summary

This supplementary document provides additional material in support of the main manuscript. It expands the hydro-climatic characterization of the 531 CAMELS-US basins and the adopted six-cluster regionalization framework; reports additional descriptive summaries of basin and cluster attributes; documents the diagnostic analyses used to interpret lower-skill basins, seasonal differences, and interannual variations in benchmark skill; and presents seed-level robustness checks for the proposed optimized ensemble frameworks. These materials show that benchmark behaviour varies systematically with hydrologic regime, seasonal runoff conditions, and interannual variability, and that the performance gains of the optimized Top-10 and cluster-wise ensemble frameworks remain stable across repeated random-seed realizations.

*Corresponding author.

Email address: farzad.hosseini@alumnos.unican.es (Farzad Hosseini)

Supplementary Materials

This supplementary document provides additional context, robustness checks, and diagnostic analyses supporting the main manuscript. It has four main purposes: (i) to expand the hydro-climatic characterization of the 531 CAMELS-US basins and the adopted six-cluster regionalization framework, (ii) to document the hydrologic diagnostics used to interpret lower-skill basins, seasonal performance differences, and interannual variations in skill, (iii) to evaluate the robustness of the benchmark comparison across repeated random-seed realizations, and (iv) to provide additional seed-level diagnostics for representative water years.

S1. Basin and cluster characterization

The following supplementary figures and tables provide additional hydro-climatic context for the 531 CAMELS-US basins used in the main manuscript and for the six-cluster regionalization framework adopted in this study. Their purpose is to complement the main-text description with expanded descriptive statistics and supporting visualizations that further characterize climatic gradients, multivariate attribute-space separation, and the regional composition of the clusters.

Figure S1 provides additional support for the interpretation that the six clusters, which are defined from static catchment attributes, are also characterized by distinct climatic, topographic, and runoff-related signatures. These contrasts help contextualize part of the variation in model behavior discussed later in the manuscript.

Figure S2 should be interpreted as an exploratory visualization rather

Climatic and topographic gradients across the six clusters

Figure S1: Distribution of key climatic and topographic attributes across the six clusters, including mean precipitation, aridity, snow fraction, mean elevation, mean slope, and catchment area. This figure complements the hydrological-signature analysis presented in the main text by showing that the clusters also differ systematically in their climatic forcing and physiographic setting. In particular, it highlights contrasts between wetter and drier clusters, lowland and mountainous groups, and snow-influenced versus rainfall-dominated basins.

25 than a formal clustering validation metric. Its main purpose is to show that several clusters occupy clearly different regions of attribute space, further supporting the hydrologic relevance of the adopted regionalization framework.

Figure S3 shows that some clusters are strongly concentrated within a
30 small number of HUC-02 regions, whereas others include basins from multiple major hydrologic regions. This pattern further supports the interpreta-

tion that the clustering captures hydro-climatic similarity rather than merely geographic proximity.

Table S1 extends the whole-sample description provided in the main text and quantifies the broad hydro-climatic range represented by the 531 study
35 basins.

Table S2 provides the detailed numerical basis underlying the cluster comparisons discussed in the main text and supports a more granular interpretation of cluster-specific climatic, physiographic, and hydrologic differences.

40 Table S3 complements the continuous hydro-climatic summaries by highlighting broad categorical descriptors of the basin groups. Although these descriptors are not used as the primary basis for interpretation, they help contextualize the dominant environmental character of each cluster.

Taken together, Figures S1–S3 and Tables S1–S3 provide additional descriptive support for the main-text conclusion that the six-cluster framework reflects meaningful hydro-climatic organization within the 531-basin CAMELS-US benchmark. These supplementary materials are intended to improve transparency, provide expanded descriptive context, and facilitate future comparison with alternative regionalization and modeling strategies.

50 *S2. Supplementary diagnostics for lower-skill, seasonal, and interannual behavior*

The main manuscript focuses on the benchmark comparison, the hydrologic-geographic structure of skill, and the interpretation of the remaining lower-skill subset. The present section provides the supplementary diagnostic
55 figures that informed that interpretation. These analyses are intentionally placed in the Supplementary Materials because they are more detailed and

Table S1: Overall hydro-climatic summary statistics for the 531 CAMELS-US basins used in this study. The table reports descriptive statistics across the full benchmark sample after joining the CAMELS-US attribute files with the 531-basin cluster-assignment file. Q5 and Q95 denote the 5th and 95th percentiles, respectively.

Attribute	Unit	Q5	Mean	SD	Q25	Median	Q75	Q95
Catchment area	km ²	22	477	473	126	310	693	1563
Mean elevation	m	56	728	788	249	437	823	2679
Mean slope	m km ⁻¹	3.2	46.2	47.3	7.4	29.0	72.6	139.8
Mean precipitation	mm d ⁻¹	1.51	3.39	1.37	2.57	3.27	3.82	6.49
Potential evapotranspiration	mm d ⁻¹	2.08	2.77	0.54	2.32	2.66	3.13	3.79
Aridity index	–	0.34	0.97	0.51	0.68	0.84	1.10	2.03
Snow fraction	–	0.00	0.17	0.20	0.04	0.10	0.22	0.69
Mean discharge	mm d ⁻¹	0.10	1.60	1.55	0.76	1.18	1.82	5.48
Runoff ratio	–	0.06	0.41	0.23	0.26	0.36	0.53	0.88
Baseflow index	–	0.18	0.48	0.16	0.40	0.50	0.59	0.72
Flow-duration-curve slope	–	0.34	1.27	0.50	0.94	1.31	1.65	2.01
High-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	1.5	23.9	26.0	6.2	14.6	35.5	68.5
Low-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.6	107.4	79.5	41.3	97.5	160.5	255.2
Zero-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.00	0.03	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14

diagnostic in nature than the core benchmark figures shown in the main text. Their role is not to introduce an additional benchmark result, but to document the empirical basis for the discussion of why skill varies across basin
60 classes, seasons, and water years.

Throughout this section, the threshold $NSE < 0.5$ is used as a diagnostic definition of a lower-skill subset. It is not intended as a universal statement of model adequacy or inadequacy. Rather, it provides a transparent and reproducible way to isolate the part of the benchmark population in which
65 performance is meaningfully below the otherwise strong regional standard achieved by the cluster-wise framework.

Figure S4 provides the multivariate diagnostic basis for the interpretation of the lower-skill subset in the discussion. The strongest negative contrasts are associated with runoff ratio, mean discharge, and several seasonal
70 runoff-related quantities, while positive contrasts are associated with aridity, interannual runoff-ratio variability, zero-flow indicators, and training-period variability metrics. This confirms that the lower-skill subset is characterized more by difficult hydrologic behavior than by a simple absence of usable data.

Figure S5 shows that the weaker water years are not characterized by an
75 even increase in lower-skill cases across the full domain. Instead, the counts are dominated by specific clusters, especially Cluster 3. This supports the interpretation that weaker years become challenging primarily when basin-year behavior shifts into already difficult hydrologic regimes rather than because the benchmark loses skill uniformly everywhere.

80 Figure S6 provides the attribute-level explanation for why some water years are more challenging than others. The lower-skill basin-year cases in

weaker years are systematically associated with drier, less runoff-efficient, and more intermittent conditions. This pattern is consistent with the main-text interpretation that temporal performance decreases are linked to shifts
85 toward hydro-climatic regimes in which runoff generation is weaker, more episodic, and less identifiable from the available predictors.

Figure S7 shows that JAS is not only the weakest season in median performance, but also the season with the largest concentration of lower-skill basin-season cases. The seasonal pattern is again cluster-dependent rather
90 than spatially uniform, reinforcing the interpretation that summer difficulty arises primarily in particular runoff regimes.

Figure S8 documents the hydrologic signature of the JAS performance loss discussed in the main manuscript. The lower-skill JAS cases are not random seasonal losses; they are concentrated in basin-season conditions
95 characterized by low runoff efficiency, low flow, weak snow influence, and a more intermittent warm-season hydrologic signal.

Figure S9 complements the JAS case-based analysis by moving from seasonal events to basin-level behavior. Basins with stronger JAS performance loss tend to lack the stronger snow-related and runoff-related seasonal organization seen in the more predictable groups, which supports the main-text
100 interpretation that seasonal structure itself is a relevant component of predictability.

Figure S10 summarizes the interannual ordering of basin-wise benchmark performance. It provides a compact complement to the more detailed water-year analyses reported in the main text and helps situate the weak-year
105 diagnostics shown above within the overall ranking of test-period water years.

Taken together, Figures S4–S10 show that the lower-skill subset, the weaker water years, and the most challenging seasonal conditions share a coherent hydrologic signature. In all three cases, the most difficult situations
110 are associated with drier, less runoff-efficient, and more intermittent conditions, whereas stronger seasonal organization and snow influence are more closely associated with stable and high benchmark skill. These supplementary analyses therefore provide the empirical basis for the discussion in the main manuscript regarding hydrologic geography, JAS performance loss, interannual non-uniformity, and the interpretation of the remaining lower-skill
115 cases.

S3. Overall benchmark robustness across random seeds

To complement the basin-wise comparison in the main text, we evaluated the robustness of the three benchmark frameworks across repeated
120 random-seed realizations. In these diagnostics, model performance was first aggregated across the 531 basins for each seed, and the resulting seed-level distributions were then compared across frameworks. These analyses are supplementary because they do not change the main benchmark ranking established in the manuscript, but they are useful for verifying that the observed
125 gains are not driven by a single favorable random initialization.

Figure S11 shows that the seed-level performance distributions are well separated. The reference benchmark occupies the lowest range, the Top-10 family is consistently improved relative to the benchmark, and the cluster-wise family achieves the highest seed-level central tendency. This indicates
130 that the advantage of the proposed optimized frameworks is not tied to a single seed realization, but is maintained across repeated runs.

Figure S12 provides the corresponding cumulative-distribution view. The curves confirm that both optimized frameworks systematically outperform the benchmark across the full set of random-seed realizations, with the cluster-wise family occupying the highest performance range and the Top-10 family remaining intermediate between the cluster-wise family and the reference benchmark.

Taken together, Figures S11 and S12 support the interpretation that the improvements reported in the main text are robust with respect to random initialization. In other words, the outperformance of the optimized ensemble frameworks reflects a stable property of the proposed benchmark design rather than a favorable outcome from a particular seed.

S4. Water-year seed-level robustness diagnostics

To complement the water-year basin-wise analyses presented in the main text, we also examined robustness across repeated random-seed realizations for selected representative water years. In these supplementary diagnostics, performance was first aggregated across the 531 basins for each seed, and the resulting seed-level values were then compared across the three benchmark frameworks. These figures are intended to verify that the interannual performance differences highlighted in the main manuscript are not driven by isolated random initializations, but instead reflect stable behavior across repeated runs.

We presented two representative water years for illustration: WY1992 and WY1998. These years provide complementary examples of benchmark behavior under comparatively more challenging and more favorable performance conditions. Across these sample cases, the same general ordering is

preserved: the two proposed frameworks remain stronger than the reference benchmark, and the cluster-wise family most often achieves the highest and most stable seed-level behavior.

160 Figures S13 and S14 show that the stronger performance of the optimized frameworks is preserved even in a year with comparatively lower overall performance. The benchmark occupies the weakest seed-level range, the Top-10 family improves on that range, and the cluster-wise family remains strongest.

165 Taken together, Figures S13–S16 support the interpretation that the interannual improvements highlighted in the main text are robust to random initialization. The advantage of the optimized ensemble frameworks, and especially of the cluster-wise family, therefore appears to be a stable property of the benchmark design rather than a favorable outcome from a particular seed realization.

Figure S2: Two-dimensional PCA representation of the six clusters in hydro-climatic attribute space. The analysis is based on selected climatic, topographic, and hydrological descriptors, while arrows indicate the loadings of the original variables on the first two principal components. This visualization provides an exploratory summary of the multivariate separation between clusters and of the variables contributing most strongly to that separation.

Figure S3: Regional composition of the six clusters by USGS 2-digit hydrologic region (HUC-02), expressed as the percentage of basins contributed by each major hydrologic region.

Table S2: Cluster-wise hydro-climatic summary statistics for the six CAMELS-US clusters. Values are reported as median [Q25–Q75] across basins within each cluster. This table provides a more detailed numerical characterization of the cluster contrasts summarized in the main manuscript.

Attribute	Unit	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
Catchment area	km ²	568 [249–944]	246 [121–520]	436 [192–893]	229 [79–526]	175 [47–431]	364 [133–864]
Mean elevation	m	292 [229–375]	418 [263–597]	684 [447–1137]	728 [486–922]	2484 [2050–3003]	71 [35–127]
Mean slope	m km ⁻¹	6.4 [4.0–8.7]	33.0 [14.1–52.2]	20.8 [9.9–60.7]	112.1 [90.3–126.7]	106.5 [84.2–137.3]	5.0 [2.6–7.4]
Mean precipitation	mm d ⁻¹	2.77 [2.60–3.21]	3.50 [3.21–3.88]	1.83 [1.36–2.40]	6.29 [5.09–7.21]	2.41 [1.81–2.84]	3.68 [3.32–3.96]
Potential evapotranspiration	mm d ⁻¹	2.58 [2.44–2.72]	2.55 [2.27–2.86]	3.37 [2.96–3.53]	2.17 [2.06–2.43]	3.00 [2.69–3.33]	3.19 [2.64–3.61]
Aridity index	–	0.90 [0.85–1.02]	0.73 [0.64–0.82]	1.75 [1.48–2.18]	0.36 [0.29–0.48]	1.38 [1.01–1.60]	0.87 [0.81–0.97]
Snow fraction	–	0.08 [0.06–0.10]	0.10 [0.04–0.20]	0.02 [0.00–0.16]	0.14 [0.05–0.32]	0.66 [0.49–0.71]	0.00 [0.00–0.05]
Mean discharge	mm d ⁻¹	0.79 [0.58–0.98]	1.48 [1.10–1.88]	0.21 [0.07–0.38]	5.36 [3.58–6.26]	1.23 [0.68–1.74]	1.05 [0.87–1.30]
Runoff ratio	–	0.28 [0.22–0.32]	0.42 [0.34–0.50]	0.11 [0.05–0.17]	0.78 [0.65–0.95]	0.53 [0.33–0.66]	0.30 [0.25–0.37]
Baseflow index	–	0.31 [0.23–0.42]	0.51 [0.44–0.57]	0.35 [0.18–0.52]	0.55 [0.51–0.60]	0.61 [0.53–0.65]	0.49 [0.41–0.62]
Flow-duration-curve slope	–	0.92 [0.72–1.30]	1.51 [1.29–1.73]	0.53 [0.22–1.06]	1.80 [1.55–2.02]	0.96 [0.77–1.27]	1.30 [0.99–1.58]
High-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	35.6 [18.4–45.5]	8.8 [5.4–15.6]	36.4 [16.7–77.6]	8.2 [3.2–16.8]	29.0 [13.1–47.4]	13.6 [2.8–28.6]
Low-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	179.2 [127.4–207.0]	75.2 [36.9–106.6]	212.4 [105.6–274.2]	96.8 [47.5–131.4]	76.1 [12.5–151.8]	85.2 [14.1–140.5]
Zero-flow frequency	d yr ⁻¹	0.00 [0.00–0.03]	0.00 [0.00–0.00]	0.04 [0.00–0.24]	0.00 [0.00–0.00]	0.00 [0.00–0.00]	0.00 [0.00–0.00]

Table S3: Dominant categorical characteristics of each cluster, including the most frequent geology class, dominant land-cover type, and principal USGS 2-digit hydrologic region (HUC-02) contributions. Percentages are computed relative to the number of basins in each cluster.

Cluster	<i>n</i>	Dominant geology class	Dominant land-cover type	Main HUC-02 contributions
C1	83	Carbonate sedimentary rocks (39.8%)	Croplands (50.6%)	10 Missouri (31.3%); 07 Upper Mississippi (31.3%); 05 Ohio (13.3%)
C2	195	Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks (50.8%)	Deciduous Broadleaf Forest (51.3%)	02 Mid-Atlantic (29.7%); 03 South Atlantic-Gulf (23.1%); 05 Ohio (12.3%)
C3	67	Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks (29.9%)	Grasslands (41.8%)	12 Texas-Gulf (38.8%); 15 Lower Colorado (19.4%); 18 California (16.4%)
C4	61	Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks (39.3%)	Evergreen Needleleaf Forest (90.2%)	17 Pacific Northwest (88.5%); 18 California (9.8%); 01 New England (1.6%)
C5	66	Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks (25.8%)	Grasslands (48.5%)	17 Pacific Northwest (25.8%); 10 Missouri (21.2%); 14 Upper Colorado (21.2%)
C6	59	Unconsolidated sediments (67.8%)	Woody Savannas (47.5%)	03 South Atlantic-Gulf (55.9%); 04 Great Lakes (15.3%); 02 Mid-Atlantic (11.9%)

Figure S4: Standardized mean differences between basins in the lower-skill subset (NSE < 0.5) and the remaining basins for selected hydro-climatic, physiographic, and training-data diagnostics. Positive values indicate variables that are larger, on average, in the lower-skill subset, whereas negative values indicate variables that are smaller. The figure shows that the lower-skill basins are associated with higher aridity, stronger runoff and precipitation variability, higher zero-flow tendency, and lower runoff efficiency, mean flow, and seasonal runoff-related signatures.

Counts of basin-year cases with NSE < threshold in weaker water years

Figure S5: Counts of basin-year cases with NSE < 0.5 in the weaker water years identified in the cluster-wise benchmark. Bars are stacked by hydrologic cluster. The figure shows that lower-skill basin-year cases in weaker years are concentrated mainly in Cluster 3, with smaller contributions from several of the remaining clusters.

Figure S6: Standardized mean differences between lower-skill basin-year cases in weaker water years and the remaining basin-year cases. Positive values denote variables that are larger in the weaker-year lower-skill subset. The figure shows that weaker-year low-skill cases are associated with higher aridity, higher zero-flow and low-flow indicators, and lower runoff efficiency, mean discharge, and flow-duration-curve slope.

Figure S7: Counts of basin-season cases with $NSE < 0.5$ by season and hydrologic cluster. The seasonal concentration of lower-skill cases is strongest in JAS, where the counts are elevated across multiple clusters, especially in the more challenging hydrologic groups.

Figure S8: Standardized mean differences between lower-skill basin-season cases in JAS and the remaining basin-season cases. Positive values denote variables that are larger in the lower-skill JAS subset. The figure shows that lower-skill JAS cases are associated with higher aridity, stronger precipitation-zero frequency, and higher low-flow or zero-flow indicators, while runoff ratio, mean discharge, snow fraction, elevation, and flow-duration-curve slope are lower.

Figure S9: Standardized mean differences between basins with pronounced JAS performance loss and the remaining basins. Positive values denote variables that are larger in basins with stronger JAS performance loss, whereas negative values denote variables that are smaller. The figure shows that these basins tend to have lower snow influence, weaker spring and summer runoff signatures, and lower elevation, suggesting that stronger seasonal runoff organization may be associated with more stable warm-season model performance.

Figure S10: Ranking of water years by median basin-wise NSE for the cluster-wise benchmark framework. The figure provides a compact visual summary of the relative interannual performance ordering and highlights the weaker and stronger years used in the discussion.

Figure S11: Distribution of seed-level NSE values computed after averaging over the 531 basins for each seed. The cluster-wise family shows the highest and most stable seed-level performance, while the Top-10 family also remains consistently stronger than the reference benchmark.

Figure S12: CDF of seed-level NSE values computed after averaging over the 531 basins for each seed. The distributional separation confirms that both proposed frameworks, especially the cluster-wise family, maintain stronger performance than the reference benchmark across repeated seeded realizations.

Distribution of seed-level NSE values in WY1992 after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Figure S13: Distribution of seed-level NSE values in WY1992 after averaging over the 531 basins for each seed. Even in this relatively more challenging year, both proposed frameworks remain above the benchmark across repeated random-seed realizations, with the cluster-wise family providing the strongest seed-level performance.

CDF of seed-level NSE values in WY1992 after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Figure S14: CDF of seed-level NSE values in WY1992 after averaging over the 531 basins for each seed. The cumulative distributions confirm a systematic seed-level advantage of the proposed frameworks relative to the benchmark.

Distribution of seed-level NSE values in WY1998 after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Figure S15: Distribution of seed-level NSE values in WY1998 after averaging over the 531 basins for each seed. In this stronger-performance year, the cluster-wise family again exhibits the highest and most stable seed-level behavior.

CDF of seed-level NSE values in WY1998 after averaging over the 531 CAMELS-US basins

Figure S16: CDF of seed-level NSE values in WY1998 after averaging over the 531 basins for each seed. The figure confirms that the gain of the proposed frameworks over the benchmark persists under repeated random-seed realizations even in a relatively strong year.